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WIDENING THE BOUNDARIES OF TECHNOLOGY: IMPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON LAW AND SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

There is increasing reliance on technology points towards future where integration with artificially intelligent systems becomes inevitable. While this assertion may spark debate, there's no denying that AI represents the future trajectory of technological advancement. Throughout history, each industrial revolution has paved the way for the evolution of various sectors, culminating in the digital age we now inhabit. In today's rapidly advancing tech landscape, artificial intelligence is gaining significant traction. However, it's essential to recognize that along with the promise of AI come accompanying complexities, some of which may have adverse societal repercussions and raise novel legal quandaries. Embracing AI or merging with artificially intelligent machines can potentially reshape every aspect of human existence, introducing legal uncertainties in its wake. Addressing these legal questions promptly is crucial to prevent a growing chasm between technological progress and legal application. While technology undoubtedly brings societal benefits, its ethical deployment hinges on vigilant regulatory frameworks. Insufficient regulation gives rise to concerns such as infringement, procedural invalidation, and the impact on intellectual property rights, criminal liability, competitive landscapes, and, most importantly, human welfare. The current legal landscape in India fails to adequately address the nuances of AI, exacerbating the challenges associated with its integration into society. Given the problematic status of AI within existing legal frameworks, it's imperative to identify and confront the challenges it presents on a global scale. This paper aims to shed light on the societal and legal ramifications of artificial intelligence, with a particular focus on its implications for patent and competition laws.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technology, law and society, Digital world

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INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence is rightly addressed as fourth industrial revolution as it widened the boundaries of use of technology, not just in terms of its role played in human life but also regarding legal field. Undoubtedly, Artificial Intelligence has implications on every field and sphere of human life, creating legal uncertainty. It is pertinent to note that with the advent of Artificial Intelligence comes up the parallel complexities, having adverse societal impact raising new legal questions. As a matter of fact, though law is not static it indeed is definite regarding its overall application. This non-static nature of law is much more pertinent when it deals with technology as such. Thus, the legal questions concerning the digitalized area and technological implications on the human subsistence need to be addressed instantly and very often to avoid an increasing gap between legal application and interpretation of law. The acceleration in technological advancements and innovations implausibly reached different level all together with artificial intelligence gaining the predominance in the market. With further advancements in technology, the artificial intelligence and the ability to use artificial intelligence tools earlier seen as unachievable, today made its stand. In fact, artificial intelligence had changed the workforce and many view it as a ‘job killer’. As always, the flip side of the coin it is expected to make things easier, avoid repetitive roles and keep the individuals more engaging and focused on the parts of their jobs that’s more productive and satisfying.

This uptrend in deployment of artificial intelligence though recent, reflects in companies ranging from startups to long-established institutions in every sector. The implications of espousing the technology or merging with artificially intelligent machines can have serious impact on every field and sphere of human life, creating legal uncertainty. The legal questions pertaining to Artificial Intelligence need to be addressed immediately to avoid an increasing gap between technological upgrade and application of law. This paper highlights the growth of AI and its

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impact on society and law. Although technology has implications on several laws the paper highlights its impact on patent laws and competition law.

GROWTH OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS IMPACT ON SOCIETY

Several definitions of artificial intelligence exist, and it changes based on the goals the author is trying to achieve with an artificial intelligence system. India's 18-member task force defines artificial intelligence as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs", with 'intelligence' being "the computational part of the ability to achieve goals in the world".¹ Further, the NITI Aayog discussion paper classifies artificial intelligence as "a constellation of technologies that enable machines to act with higher levels of intelligence and emulate the human capabilities of sense, comprehension and action".²

For simple understanding, artificial intelligence can be categorized as technology that is "created by a human, improved by a machine and has the power to disrupt almost all aspects of human existence".³ Technology so developed could be three types that is strong artificial intelligence, the one being able to behave intelligently by thinking as a human. Second super intelligence AI, which has the capability to even surpass humans. And lastly, the weak AI which behaves intelligently but does not possess consciousness about what it is doing. The last kind of technology is 'narrow' in its approach and is limited to a single task. This technology involves direct human intervention in its creation. The probability of the explosion of artificial intelligence technology is much stronger. The next phase will bring in the 'strong artificial

¹Pankaj Soni&Kartikay Vikrant Singh, 'Are we ready for AI disruption? An Indian patent law perspective', (IP Law Galli, 2019) <<https://www.remfry.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Print-PDF.pdf>> accessed 19th December 2023.

²VartulMittal, 'Think Big Start Small',(Sharedservicesforumb, 2020) <<https://sharedservicesforum.in/think-big-start-small>>accessed 2nd January 2024.

³Janna Anderson & Lee Rainie, 'Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Humans', (Pew Research Centre, 10 December 2018) <<https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/12/10/artificial-intelligence-and-the-future-of-humans/>>accessed 2nd January 2024

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intelligence’, wherein the system thinks as humans do, having conscious and subjective mind. Such technology will be closer to human intelligence and capable of completing a wide range of tasks. And that the concerns arise with emergence of strong artificial intelligence as they believe to hold capability of human intelligence, which may evolve further to create improved systems of artificial intelligence.

Technology today evidently plays a major role in our daily activities, in fact has become part of our life. One such technology that holds a predominant impact on every aspect of human sphere is artificial intelligence. From the inception and use of artificial intelligence, it has been very difficult to understand and measure whether the positive impact outweighs the negative effects or vice versa. It is an interesting development that not just has an impact on one component or sector of the society but does holds a significant role to play in every segment. From use of robotics to automated entertainment, from cellphones to anything and everything in economy there is reflection of artificial intelligence application.⁴ In short, Artificial intelligence has changed the dynamics of market by changing the way working structures of multiple industries. As stated earlier, artificial intelligence has a great impact on every sphere of human life and below are the few segments in which the developments make the impact very evident.

- **Governance:** Indian government is more inclined towards building “Digital India”⁵. In the process, we have reached at an hour where we can see more efficient bureaucracy with much quicker responses and involving less paperwork, duration, processes etc. It is

⁴Darrell M West & John R Allen, *How Artificial Intelligence is Transforming the World* (Brookings, 24 April 2018) <<https://www.brookings.edu/research/how-artificial-intelligence-is-transforming-the-world/>> accessed on 3rd January 2024.

⁵Nilu Singh, ‘Digital India: To Transform India into A Digitally Empowered Society’, (ResearchGate, December 2017) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321722968_Digital_India_To_Transform_India_into_A_Digitally_Empowered_Society> accessed on 6th January 2024.

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definite that artificial intelligence not just changed the way people interact but also drastically changed the public administration system and patterns.

- **Health care system:** National Digital Health Mission 2020⁶ makes every Indian eligible to get health ID card which will be a repository of all health related information of an individual. Artificial intelligence has been vividly used in the implementation of the said mission, which ensures that it has the potential to make health care system much more accessible and more affordable. Artificial intelligence will also help the doctors to start the treatment immediately in case of an emergency as the data pertaining to the individual's health is retrieved easily. It will be more accurate, convenient and as well involves less costs.
- **Improving economy:** There are several issues and concerns that India is dealing with today. One such major problem is prevailing unemployment and the rate at which it is increasing. Artificial intelligence has the potential to create more jobs and change the way people worked bringing in more productivity and outcome. It is paving way for new enterprises, leaving all together a new scope for earnings. Artificial intelligence has the potential to overcome the physical limitations such as capital and labor and capture the total productivity paving way to the growth of new sources adding value to the economy.
- **Social development:** Artificial intelligence holds a transformative impact which could be worked towards the greater good. It has the potential to improve the quality of life and access to the larger section of the world. However, it can work as a real time advisor,

⁶BalakrushnaPadhi& Udaya Mishra, 'Concerns around the NDHM (National Digital Health Mission)', Economic and Political Weekly (ResearchGate, 10 September 2020) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344154785_Concerns_around_the_NDHM_National_Digital_Health_Mission>accessed on 6th January 2024.

predict unforeseen factors, and increase productivity, built smart and efficient cities with suitable infrastructure adhering to the demands of the society.⁷

- **Education:** Artificial intelligence has the skill of augmenting and learning and has inbuilt potential to provide accurate solutions with quality, expediting administrative tasks and improve access issues prevailing in the Indian education sector.
- **Banking and financial sector:** India has seen an upsurge in implementation of artificial intelligence-based banking and finance system in recent times. Banking has become much easier with the Fintech coming into place.⁸ Artificial intelligence has improved the process through deployment of intelligent machines for back-office operations, credit scores analysis, fraud analysts, virtual customer assistance etc.

These developments and opportunities come with risk associated. If the individuals are not equipped with the knowledge to use the artificial intelligence it can well bring in a disadvantage and might also increase in unemployment rates. The technological development is changing the functioning of the society and that the digitization is a challenge to the way we live. Systems are becoming more capable blurring the line between online and offline. It is very soon that the technology will be dispersed around us change the way we live, ensuring smart cities. Despite all the advantages artificial intelligence is capable to deliver, artificial intelligence has the potential impact on human subsistence. However, all the above discussed points have flip side as implementation of any without a proper framework or infrastructure might costs us a lot. Artificial intelligence not just had changed the shape or functioning of industries but has

⁷Yerragola Prakash, 'Smart Cities Mission in India: An Empirical study on opportunities and Challenges', (ResearchGate, 3 October 2020) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324503184_Smart_Cities_Mission_in_India_An_Empirical_study_on_opportunities_and_Challenges> accessed on 3rd January 2024.

⁸C Vijai, 'Fintech in India – Opportunities and Challenges', (SSRN Electronic Journal, 2 December 2019) <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3354094>> accessed on 10th January 2024.

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immensely modified the manner that human interacts with each other and the world. The legal system of a Country is said to be vast and inclusive of all the spheres. That with the advent of artificial intelligence the legal system is constantly changing, and it is important for the stakeholders to involve in active debates to ensure the positive impact of artificial intelligence on society.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LAW

The major function that laws does is ensuring a specific conduct in the society. Consequently, the entire conduct of humans including the machines that human use such as computers, cars, etc. is governed by set of rules and regulations. Thus, it is universally accepted that law has wider scope and that it describes, explains, permits and regulates every aspect of the societal functioning. And yet another thing that we experience it everywhere is system of artificial intelligence, from entertainment to serious business it has proven its potential to be a part of every activity. The research and development are now focusing on ‘reinforcement learning’ of the artificial intelligence systems, which means that the artificial intelligence will be equipped to learn from its past experiences. Over the past few years, artificial intelligence with integrated reinforcement learning has been adopted not just in hardware and software solutions but the application is seen in almost everything, from AI-controlled signals to drones.

Now that the law is not static and the same is being the status of artificial intelligence, the concerns regarding the legal system and the treatment that could be given to the reinforcement learning capability of artificial intelligence. The concerns such as rights, liability become much problematic to be addressed. However, it is essentially the need of the hour to ensure that law adapts to this technological development soon. The paper will further highlight the implications of artificial intelligence on two major laws i.e., Patent and Competition law. Also lay emphasis on legal and ethical issues involved in recognition of artificial intelligence.

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND PATENT: BACKGROUND

As the relevance of protecting innovations by registering for patent is very evident, it is pertinent to consider what constitutes invention for the purposes of obtaining patent protection and as well try to understand the why artificial intelligence's creation or innovations do not placate the said parameters. If carefully observed a primary requirement for qualifying to be an inventor is "making a significant contribution to the invention and to meet this standard, one must bring about a definite and permanent idea of the invention, sufficient to allow a skilled artisan to carry out the invention without undue experimentation." Careful analysis of the provisions of patent law will raise certain queries as to who should be considered as the inventor, is it artificial intelligence applications or human being who he is responsible for the creation of the said artificial intelligence application. However, it is very significant to protect the intellectual property and that the stakeholders of the enterprise should be aware of the key indicators to be taken into consideration in its application to artificial intelligence's innovations. As protecting intellectual property encourages innovation and creativity by avoid duplication. The growth of patent filing in past few years help us understand the growing concern not only to protect the creation of Artificial Intelligence but also to develop a regulatory framework to govern and protect the innovations created by Artificial Intelligence. Though seems simple but involves complexities in implementing the same. It is relevant for one to understand that recognition of artificial intelligence and granting protection is one step ahead, whereas recognition of work generated by Artificial Intelligence is yet another step towards future. And the patent law in India will face the implications of artificial intelligence's innovation.

It is not wide of the mark in averring that the future of innovation is the inventions by artificial intelligence. If you profoundly analyze, until the groundbreaking innovation is achieved any invention for instance is considered to involve a story of long genius relentlessly toiling in a garage. The patterns of modern businesses infuse artificial intelligence and thus entrusting the

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value of powerful tool of innovation. Taking into consideration the pace at which the patent filing for inventions of artificial intelligence is seen upsurge worldwide, it is believed that artificial intelligence in no time be the prominent factor responsible for most inventions. Herein which the major issue persists. The provisions of Patent Law in India focus on innovations by human interference, however the uncertainty as to how to treat technologies that are solely created by the computers without human intervention or engagement within the existing provisions of law continues. Not merely the treatment but also concerns as to grant of patents for artificial intelligence's inventions should be addressed by the concerned authorities viz., legislative body and courts. The existing uncertainty regarding the application of law might majorly result in patentees' preference of not disclosing the computer's invention.

The complication persists if a human inventor is to be considered for the patent registration, firstly whether the indications should be set by the law, or should this decision be left to private arrangements of the parties involved in such processes and leave the possibility of judicial intervention in accordance with existing laws concerning inventorship disputes. The essential indicator that is to be mandatorily investigated for obtaining the eligibility is the nature of any invention. It should be qualified to be unique in its characteristics and the intended use. Let us understand the implications of artificial intelligence's innovations on patent law in India. Given the pragmatic view to the provisions of Patent Act, it is definite that in any invention, the inventor and the owner could be involved and that they need not be the same and both could be part of the registration. The artificial intelligence predominantly play an important role in the segment where there exists a direct relationship of human with the artificial intelligence i.e., "to augment human life and enhance or extend human capabilities through a direct relationship between human interaction with the AI"⁹ and the other category is of the artificial intelligence identified and considered as the source of the invention and accepted for patent registration in its

⁹ Ibid.

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name i.e., “an autonomous, making decisions within a contextual solution space and are being employed by humans to serve them” it is definitely significant to identify the source of invention and maintain a proper record for tracking down the world civilization advances itself. Now the underlying issue is that should human based entities employing artificial intelligence be considered for registration and allow a claim of inventorship or should artificial intelligence as a standalone claim the inventorship. Even if artificial intelligence is allowed to claim the title of an inventor “what are the rights of an artificial intelligence?”

However, doing so would open the scope for underlying complications. Starting from what kind of rights to employability of such rights, from human acknowledgment of artificial intelligence as their equals to acceptance of same rights granted to artificial intelligence. Several contemplations are made in this regard “humans will not accept AI as their equals, and grant them the same rights, and eventually work for them.”¹⁰ In that sense, AI cannot own property. Now, by and large, we as humans are not even always able to acknowledge equal rights with regards to our own diversity.

IMPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON PATENT LAWS

Recognizing and registration of inventions created by artificial intelligence involves intricacies concerning the concepts prevailing in Patent law. As it is rightly understood that artificial intelligence is created and owned by the human, meaning that, given a particular timeframe, or indefinite period as it owns, the output and benefits of such employability of the artificial intelligence is to be owned by the entities based and operated by human, artificial intelligence is working for. The question persists as to transferability of such intellectual property. And also, the concerns pertaining to exclusion of patent protection to artificial intelligence autonomously

¹⁰Jessica Peng, ‘How Human is AI and Should AI Be Granted Rights?’, (Jessica Peng, 4 December 2018) <<http://blogs.cuit.columbia.edu/jp3864/2018/12/04/how-human-is-ai-and-should-ai-be-granted-rights/>>accessed on 6th January 2024.

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generated inventions prevail as the law currently fails to address the status of the existing stakeholders involved in such inventions.

However, the entities holding the strength and ascendancy in the market tends to exhibit the employability of more resources and postulates the possibility of developing artificial intelligence that can generate intellectual property eligible to be patented. If the law addresses the said concern, there is relatable issue on the duration of such protection that patents. To advance the human conditions and patentability of artificial intelligence's innovations should be re-evaluated. Likewise, the other major implication on patent laws is concerning the patentable subject matter and guidelines on patentable inventions. The ongoing developments in the field of machine learning and automation expands the horizons, scope and patterns of artificial intelligence applications. The technology advancements have created the explosion of applications holding capacity and automatic generation or creation of patentable inventions without human interference. Although, there exists vacuum regarding the holder of the "title" under patent law as to exclude autonomously generated artificial intelligence application from the eligibility of patentability by itself. It is important at the juncture, to understand that an invention is an invention, created by human or artificial intelligence should be allowed to be registered. If done otherwise, would strongly vitiate the whole purpose of the intellectual property policy.

If it is keenly taken note of, the new millennium in the last few decades as majorly seen three prominent revolutions. First being Industrial revolution, which transformed the reliance on agriculture-based economy to the industrial based economy. Second being the electronic revolution¹¹ which transformed the mechanical processes to the electronic modes. And

¹¹ Frederic Reamer, 'The Digital and Electronic Revolution in Social Work: Rethinking the Meaning of Ethical Practice'. (Ethics and Social Welfare, 23 March 2013)<10.1080/17496535.2012.738694> accessed on 18th January 2024.

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lastly, Network revolution¹² which has connected the people, trade and commerce around the world through digital space. Taking into consideration the explosion of information and communication technology patterns it is significant for one to understand the transformation and adaptability of the different technologies and the capacities the individual technology holds. Law in general, holds non-static nature ensuring that the changes and concerns prevailing go unaddressed. The developments should always be taken due consideration of and avoid the gaps created the advancements in different fields of societal relevance. Which moves us to the next implication that artificial intelligence possess on patent laws is to re-evaluate the requirement of introducing specific provisions for inventions specifically assisted by artificial intelligence or should they be classified and put within the brackets of computer-assisted inventions.

Yet another concern is pertinent to the procedures laid for the examination of invention filed for patent. The prevailing guidelines seem not to cover the inventions assisted by the artificial intelligence. However, it is significant to determine whether the existing provisions could be interpreted to include inventions without intervention of human, or we are at a stage, the patent laws seem archaic and requires amendments ensuring procedures for patent examination in the form of guidelines for artificial intelligence assisted inventions. And establishing or proving an invention is with or without human intervention. The aspects essential to be taken care of is the intended use and liability of the patent holder. As discussed, the concerns regarding the disclosure requirements of inventions assisted or generated by the artificial intelligence. However, with the advent of inventions by artificial intelligence's assisted or generated inventions created a major development. It is understood that the output, intended use and the liability of the creator need to be explainable to be stipulated in the form of disclosure.

If observed, it is difficult to retain the initial algorithm in machine learning as is said to change over a time with access to data. And that the major concern pertains to the question as to utility

¹² Ibid.

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of the disclosure of the initial algorithm. In simple terms, it is important to address whether it is sufficient to disclose the initial algorithm. Likewise, if the algorithm itself is to be patented yet again it is to an extent convenient. But if the patented item is a trained artificial intelligence, it gets difficult to immediately be explained algorithmically. There could be several questions to be addressed by the patent laws in existence, as to how data be used to train an algorithm and how the same could be treated for the purposes of disclosure. The major dilemma in going ahead with the application processes, should such category of data be disclosed or described. At this juncture, it is significant to discuss and bring in the general policy considerations for the patent system. To understand the implication, we must take into consideration sui generis system of intellectual property rights for artificial intelligence generated inventions. This helps us resolve the underlying issue and adjust innovation incentives for the same. It is for one to decide as these factors in consideration are too early to be raised or delayed because the impact of artificial intelligence is reflected both on science, law and technology. The explosion seen still holds the capacity of much greater impact and that yet to be unfolded at a rapid rate.

It is pertinent at this juncture to comprehend as to why there is an ongoing debate and discussion as to the status of an innovation i.e., who get to hold the title the human who created the artificial intelligence with capacity to learn and generate new ideas or the artificial intelligence itself should be given the title for AI generated inventions. The systematic analysis of the market will draw our attention to the signaling function or role that patent entrusts to an entity. In terms of entrepreneurial financial market owning a patent makes the business competitive by providing sort of leverage over the other market players. These signals allow a party to incur some cost to convey information about itself to outside firms. According to the WIPO publication 1055 – “Technology Trends 2019¹³, the most predominant AI functional applications have been filed in

¹³World Intellectual Property Organization, *Artificial Intelligence* (WIPO Technology Trends 2019) <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_1055.pdf> accessed on 25th January 2024.

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the fields of telecommunications, transportation and life and medical sciences with activity mainly in computer vision, natural language processing and speech processing.” The same publication states that "the most marked increase in patenting activity between 2013 and 2016 features machine learning technique, deep learning" with deep learning having an average annual growth rate of 175 percent in this period. And that the fastest growing artificial intelligence functional applications are robotics and control methods in the fields of aerospace, smart cities etc.¹⁴Securing a patent transmits a positive message about the state of the firm’s research and development, leading a path to a successful investment.

Adjudicating the patentability questions is one such factor is always investigated by the current patent laws. More specific, the patent concerns related to the current generation of artificial intelligence technology. It is now for the Indian government to begin carefully considering how the next generation of artificial intelligence, might be the versions of strong artificial intelligence or super-intelligence artificial intelligence, be treated in the patent ecosystem. “Does the legal responsibility arising through an artificial intelligence’s illegal action lie with it, its owner or its user or operator?” Most importantly we must derive the clarity on most debatable concept as to the possibility of humans being replaced by the machines and understand as to the probability of humans not being able to replicate the grand design of evolution on a piece of paper coded into a machine. Therefore, it pertinent to understand that the strong and super-intelligence artificial intelligence is beyond human capability. With the explosion in technology and development, it is believed that the basic knowledge, intelligence and cognitive thinking are programmable into a machine which gives it an ability to make independent decisions and generate inventions. The question that is to be addressed by the law makers today is that mere such ability be the factor to

¹⁴Javier Andreu Perez &FaniDeligianni, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Robotics’, (UK-RAS Network September 2020) <<https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1803/1803.10813.pdf>> accessed on 1st February 2024.

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determine whether a machine will get the eligibility to obtain the title of an inventor. Once this question is answered, the other aspects will eventually fall into place.

COMPETITION POLICY CONCERNS: RETHINKING THE CONTOURS

The plain reading of the aims and objectives of the competition Act 2002 draws our attention to the how freedom of trade is being ensured and protected. The Act specifically aims at achieving the three main objectives that is “To protect the interest of consumers, to promote competition in the markets and largely to eliminate practices which may adversely affect the competition”. Competition Commission of India is the constituted under the Competition Act 2002 whose imperative duty is to ensure that there is no agreement or arrangement that is having an adverse effect on the competition in the market. Any activity that cuts down the benefits of a fair and healthy competition consequentially affecting the consumer interest is curbed by CCI. That is where there is widening duties of CCI could be traced. The technological developments, specifically artificial intelligence has the potential to bring in competitive concerns and influence or predict the market dynamics. This potential of artificial intelligence is presumed to have invariably affected the competitive spirit of the market.

Artificial intelligence being most cost effective and accurate has revolutionized the world. The processes have taken over the long run regular manual processes. Although, technological development has been pervading from the inception of internet, the emergence of digital age and artificial intelligence has increased the competitive concerns in the market. The major concern being, access and sharing of information worldwide through virtual platform creating huge data and evolving new business models in the world market. This development parallelly had generated voluminous value data at every step of user’s interaction with the services created through the technology and is widely used by the enterprises to monetize their businesses. As the current landscape of businesses and shape of multiple enterprises is changed, it is evident that the algorithms are playing major role in enterprises controlling production and management

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functions. Today with artificial intelligence the data is being easily collected, processed and stored, the involvement of the enterprises in self-learning market conditions through programmed and controlling market condition in specific the demand and supply becomes much easier. These practices that the enterprise is getting into in the digital era with the help of artificial intelligence has potential to fall within the brackets of anti-competitive activities affecting the fair competition within the market.

Market power of a firm in these markets may turn out to be ephemeral.¹⁵ The business models relying on vast collection and processing of big data in nearly real-time enable players in the digital space to offer a wide range of innovative and customized services. However, the perks offered by technology come along with a potential threat of market domination by various entities through innovation itself. Artificial intelligence is certainly an innovation which poses threats of market domination.

It is important for one to understand few concepts such as “price personalization”¹⁶, “dynamic pricing”¹⁷, “two-sided market”¹⁸ “resetting”¹⁹ and “tacit price collusion”²⁰ to analyze the

¹⁵ Augustine Peter, Member, ‘Competition Comm’n of India’, (ASSOCHAM 5th International Conference on Competition Law and Tech Sector, 19 January 2018),

<<https://www.cci.gov.in/sites/default/files/speeches/Key%20Note%20Address%2C%20ASSOCHAM%205th%20International%20Conference%20on%20Competition%20Law%20and%20Tech%20Sector.pdf?download=1>>

accessed on 3rd February 2024..

¹⁶ Personalised Pricing in the Digital Era, ‘Directorate for Financial and Enterprise Affairs Competition Committee, (OECD, 28 November, 2018) [https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP\(2018\)13/en/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DAF/COMP(2018)13/en/pdf) accessed on 11th February 2024

¹⁷ Ibid

¹⁸ Lapo Filistrucchi, & Damien Geradin & Eric Damme, ‘Identifying Two-Sided Markets, World Competition’ (10 October, 2020) <10.2139/ssrn.200866> accessed on 11th February 2024.

¹⁹ Joseph E Harrington, ‘A Theory of Tacit Collusion’, (TSE, 23 September, 2020) https://www.tse-fr.eu/sites/default/files/medias/stories/SEMIN_11_12/ECONOMIC_THEORY/harrington.pdf accessed on 15th February 2024.

²⁰ Ibid.

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implications of artificial intelligence on competition law. This could be easily understood with an illustration, for instance let examine the regular and basic activity everyone is involved in or experienced that is “booking a cab”. If carefully observed when request is made by using an Ola or Uber, the app connects the driver to the end-use consumer which is nothing but two-sided market. Thus, when request is made the app using artificial intelligence examine the expected traffic and travel time along with the analysis of history and frequency of the consumer using the app set a price that reflects on the consumer screen fostering loyalty through “price personalization”. The major concern lies around the concept of price personalization as it may lead to “resetting” the market equilibrium which is more kind of an anti-competitive practice.²¹

The price fluctuation and adjustment to the costs of its competitors sometimes might not easily lead to drop in pricing reducing the possibility and probability of reduction in substituting the service with the other. This will put the players in the market at an advantageous position but is acts detrimental to the consumer welfare and reduce the benefits of fair competition within the market. That is where the major challenge is involved, mere fixing prices based on the competing prices is not anti-competitive but there is always a possibility of the competing players in the market collectively or collusively influence the market prices which is nothing but “Tacit price collusion”, which holds an adverse effect on competition within the market and as well is detriment to the consumer interest. Thus, it is the need of the hour for the regulators that is CCI to emanate the use of artificial intelligence and explore ways in which it can effectively be mitigated.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing various aspects of human life, including the legal field. While AI offers immense potential for growth and efficiency, it also presents significant

²¹ Ibid.

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legal challenges. The current legal framework struggles to keep pace with the rapid advancements in AI technology. This paper highlights the key areas where AI impacts law:

Patent Law: Uncertainties exist regarding who owns inventions created by AI and how to handle intellectual property rights.

Competition Law: AI-powered algorithms can potentially distort market competition through practices like price personalization and tacit collusion.

Suggestions

Legislative Reforms: Lawmakers need to adapt legal frameworks to address issues like inventorship rights for AI creations and regulations for AI use in commerce to promote fair competition.

Standardization: Develop international standards for responsible AI development and deployment to address ethical concerns and potential biases.

Collaboration: Encourage collaboration between legal professionals, technologists, and policymakers to create a future-proof legal system that fosters innovation while mitigating risks associated with AI.

AI is here to stay, and the legal system needs to evolve to accommodate this transformative technology. By implementing these suggestions, we can ensure that AI benefits society while minimizing potential risks.